

CONTENT-ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS

Evatov Saminjon Sobirovich

Teacher Department of Pedagogy of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382430>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-May 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 25-May 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 29-May 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

Competence approach, linguistics, sociology, social psychology, the study of competencies, competence-based, educational, professional, social, professional, qualification.

ABSTRACT

Such a definition of the learning goal limits the student's activity, as a result of which his significance, both personal and socially conscious, is lost. The only way out of such a problematic situation is to introduce a new, i.e. competent approach to general secondary education.

In modern conditions, the development of science and technology requires a radical change in the requirements for education and its results, and based on this basis, the creation of new generation standards is an important task for pedagogues. If the State educational standards created until now are based on a systematic-active approach, the purpose of general secondary schools is to develop competences aimed at self-development from the way students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities. It is required to be determined based on a functional approach. Because the essence of the educational process organized in general secondary schools is not to develop the needs and abilities of students, but mainly to convey knowledge in academic subjects in an informative and verbal manner, to form skills and competencies. Information acquired in such a reproductive way does not allow the student to develop practical experience. As a result, there are differences such as the fact that students are accumulating a lot of information in vain, the effectiveness of education is low and it does not correspond to the real reality. More precisely, it seems that the student is far away from real life, and the goal is to learn only the previously collected information. Determining the purpose of education in this way limits the student's activity, as a result, both his personal and socially understood meaning is lost.

The only way out of such a problematic situation is to introduce a new, i.e. competent, approach to general secondary education. Of course, the introduction of a competent approach to the general secondary education system requires, first of all, a comprehensive scientific study of it. Although the competent approach to general secondary education can be interpreted as a phenomenon, it should be emphasized that it is deeply understood and has its place in the science of pedagogy.

A competent approach requires the student not to acquire knowledge and skills

separately, but to master them as a whole. In connection with this demand, in turn, the system of choosing teaching methods is changing. The selection and practical application of teaching methods, in turn, requires the improvement of competencies and functions that meet the requirements of the educational process. Therefore, the competent approach is a new pedagogical reality from the point of view of modernization of general secondary education. Within this approach, practical activity experience, competence and competence are considered as didactic units, and traditional three elements of education (triad) - "Knowledge - Skill - Qualification" are divided into six units (sixtet) - "Knowledge - Knowledge". It is required to be analyzed in the form of "qualification - Qualification - Practical activity experience - Competence - Competence".

In this paragraph, the essence of the concept of communicative competence, its definition in dictionaries, its pedagogical significance, and the possibilities and current state of the educational system aimed at its formation are researched. For this purpose, it is appropriate to clarify the content of the concept of competence first.

Today, the ability to communicate effectively, which we call communicative competence, has always been of interest to many scientists. In linguistics, sociology, social psychology, pedagogy, and other modern fields of knowledge, attention is paid to the theoretical study of interpersonal relations, communicative behavior of a person.

If the dictionary of terms from pedagogy is defined as "competency - knowledge in this or that field", then in the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan "competency - 1) a specific state body (local self-government body) or official scope of powers, rights and duties of a person defined by law, charter or other document; 2) defined as knowledge, experience in one or another field.

According to the Uzbek scientist N.M. Muslimov, the dictionary meaning of the English concept of "competence" is "ability", but the term competence serves to express knowledge, skill, skill and ability.

Russian scientist N.V. Tarasova interprets the concept of "competency" as "a general ability based on knowledge, values, abilities that allows to ensure the connection between knowledge and situation, knowledge and action to solve a problem." Based on the opinion of the author, it can be concluded that competence is a person's ability to solve a certain problem based on existing knowledge and life experiences.

It should be emphasized that most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" are related to professional education and professional activity. However, since this concept has the description of innovation in connection with general secondary education, there is a special need to clarify its essence.

In fact, the concept of competence entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, in unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, and uses information full of conflicts, which develops consistently. and possessing a plan of action in complex processes. Also, competencies require constant enrichment of knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work. It is considered a real, formed personal quality based on knowledge, and it is an intellectual and personally determined social and

professional formation of a person. Also, it is defined in relation to certain objects and processes and includes a set of interrelated characteristics (knowledge, skills, methods of activity) necessary for high-quality production activities in relation to them. contains z. Therefore, a specific, isolated, special requirement for students' preparation in the educational process is considered.

The concept of "communication" (from the Latin *communico* - means common) is very broad and is used in various fields of human activity in pedagogy, psychology, linguistics, management, law, economics, etc. Today, there are a number of definitions of this concept, and it is appropriate to dwell on some of them. Communication, in a general sense, is the transfer of a message, any information. The communication process is presented as one of the important foundations of human and social life. At the same time, according to researchers, the process of communication means both itself and its result. In turn, interpersonal communication indicates that it is nothing more than the process of transferring information from one person to another person to a target object or a certain group of objects.

"Communicable", which is related to the word communication, means "having the ability to communicate", "communicable" means "approachable, cordial", as well as "communicative" - that is, "relating to communication" .

Communication is, first of all, a method of activity, which shows the adaptation of people to interaction. Therefore, communication can be considered as a kind of process of exchange of ideas, as a result of which mutual support and coordination of actions at different levels of complexity are ensured. Also, communication can be defined as one of the components of communication.

Therefore, it can be said that communicativeness is the exchange of the formation of integral symbols that reflect the ideas, thoughts, knowledge, and feelings of the communicating parties.

The research conducted by scientists in the field of communicative competence shows that it is the competences that are important in the process of education and upbringing, what to teach and how to teach, what should be formed. English language classes are no exception in this process. From this point of view, the analysis of the concept of "communicative competence" seems to be an urgent problem for us.

Research scientist E.I.Litnevskaya puts forward the following definition of communicative competence: "It is the mastery of all types of speech activity, the elements of oral and written speech culture, the basic skills and competences of language use in life areas and situations of communication at a certain age" .

Another scientist, N. I. Gez, understands communicative competence as "the ability to use language correctly in various socially determined conditions." Therefore, communicative competence includes the ability to compare speech with the purpose and situation of communication, as well as the ability to conduct communication correctly, taking into account the cultural and social norms of communicative behavior.

At this point, the perfect definition of communicative competence was given by M.R. Lvov, who stated that "communicative competence is a language and its phonetic features, lexical and grammatical units, stylistics, speech culture, this language. is a concept that means having tools and knowing the types of speech activities. Also, speaking, listening, reading, writing - within the social, professional, cultural requirements of a person, and

communicative competence will be the result of natural speech activity and special training.

Communicative competence is defined by a number of scientists as "the ability to interact with the help of language, that is, to express one's thoughts in the process of communicating with interlocutors and to use them in different situations, to correctly apply the linguistic system." are interpreted as and prefer the communicative behavior that corresponds to the norms of speech, certain communication conditions.

According to A.N.Kazarsev, "communicative competence is a collection of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for understanding strangers and creating one's own programs through speech behaviors appropriate to the goals, areas, and situations of communication. It includes knowledge of the main concepts of speech linguistics - styles, types, methods of connecting sentences in the text, etc.; text analysis skills and abilities and communication skills - oral communication skills and abilities in relation to different fields and situations of communication, taking into account the recipient and the target".

There are many approaches to what should be included in students' communicative competence. D. Haims considered it necessary to include here discursive (rules of constructing the meaning of the spoken sentence) and strategic (rules of maintaining communication with the interlocutor), grammatical (language rules) and socio-linguistic (dialect speech rules) competencies.

According to researcher A.A. Bodalyov, "the communicative side of communication consists of sharing information between people, the interactive side of communication consists of organizing mutual cooperation between individuals, that is, not only knowledge and ideas, but also information exchange with actions. ..., the perceptive side of communication consists in the process of accepting each other as a partner in communication and, therefore, a relationship of solidarity. Creating psychological conditions for the full expression of one's thoughts, worldviews, ideas of the partners with whom the person communicates, organizing a rich and diverse palette of tools, being oriented towards mastering all perceptive, communicative, interactive aspects of adequacy. need" .

According to the Russian scientist O. Kazarseva, communicative competence is "not an innate ability, but an ability that is formed by a person in the process of acquiring social-communicative experience. Communicative-social experience, first of all, includes the mechanism of changing relations and is manifested in the use of speech in stylistically different options. The basis of such a change is the change of role dialogues between the dialogue participants. So, this competence is a complex communicative skill and type of activity, new social skills, communication norms and restrictions, knowledge, customs, etiquette, manners, educational orientations.

According to research scientist N. Amirov, "the ability to communicate effectively, which today we call communicative competence, has always been of interest to many scientists. Emphasis is placed on the theoretical study of interpersonal interactions and communicative behavior of individuals in disciplines such as sociology, social psychology, pedagogy, and other modern fields of knowledge. Even now, there is a social need to increase the number of research works aimed at preparing personnel for effective communication from the time of school and increasing their knowledge about the culture of communication. For this, in the context of the formation of today's global communication space, "the importance of scientific recommendations that can be taken into account in the implementation of various

educational reforms, in particular, in the transition of the educational system to new state standards and in the training of future specialists is growing. The main goal of the modern educational process is to organize effective continuous education aimed at developing students' personal abilities, scientific potential, knowledge, skills and qualifications. So, communicativeness is a general communicative characteristic of a person, which includes communication skills, knowledge, skills and social experience.

References:

1. Glossary of terms from pedagogy. — Tashkent: Science, 2008. — 196 p.
2. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. Volume 4. Zebunniso-Konigil. — Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2002. — 704 p.
3. Muslimov N.A. Theoretical-methodical foundations of professional formation of vocational education teacher: Ped. science. doc. ... diss. - Т., 2007. -В. 130.
4. Тарасова Н.В. Мировой опыт реализации компетентностного подхода в профессиональном образовании // Среднее профессиональное образование. - 2007. - №2. - С. 36-38.
5. Юсуфбекова Н.Р. Тенденции и законы инновационных процессов в образовании. Новые исследования в педагогических науках. - М.: Педагогика, 1991.-№2. -С. 6-9.
6. Amirov N.I. Formation of students' communicative competence in the educational process. Modern education. 2020. 3. (88). -В. 26.
7. Бориснёв С.В. Социология коммуникации: Учеб. пособие для вузов. - М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА / С.В. Бориснёв - 2003. - С. 270.
8. Гальскова Н.Д. Межкультурное общение: проблема целей и содержания обучения иностранным языкам / Н.Д. Гальскова // Иностранные языки в школе. 2004. - № 1. - С. 3-8.
9. Гойхман О.Я., Надеина Т.М. Речевая коммуникация: учебник. - М.: ИНФРА-М, 2001 - С. 167.
10. Шибутани Т. Социальная психология.- Ростов н/Д:Феникс, 1999. - С. 342.
11. Социология: словарь-справочник. Т. 3. Междисциплинарные исследования. -М., 1991.
12. Литневская Е.И. Методика преподавания русского языка в средней школе: учеб. пособие для студентов высших учебных заведений / Е.И. Литневская, В.А. Багрянцева. - М.: Академический проект, 2006. - С. 588.
13. Гез Н.И. Формирование коммуникативной компетенции как объект зарубежных методических исследований / Н.И. Гез // Иностр. языки в школе. -1985. - № 2. - С. 17-24.
14. Львов М.Р. Словарь-справочник по методике преподавания русского языка: Пособие для студентов педагогических вузов и колледжей / М.Р. Львов. - М.: Издательский центр «Академия»; Высшая школа, 1999. - С. 272.
15. Сафонова, В.В. Коммуникативная компетенция: современные подходы к многоуровневому описанию в методических целях / В.В. Сафонова. - М.: Изд-во НИЦ «Еврошкола», 2004. - С. 236.
16. Казарцев А.Н. Культура речевого общения: теория и практика обучения: учебное пособие. 2-е изд. - М.: Флинта - Наука, 1999. - С. 496.6.
17. Хомский Н. Язык и проблемы знания // Вестник Московского университета.

Сер.9. Филология. 1996. – № 6. – С. 157–164.

18.Бодалев А.А. Психология общения. - М.: Изд-во Воронеж: НПО«МОДЭК», 1996. – С. 71.

19.Казарцева О.М. Культура речевого общения: Теория и практика обучения. - М.:Флинта-наука,1999. – С. 61.

20. Amirov N.I. Formation of students' communicative competence in the educational process. Modern education. 2020. 3. (88). -В. 26.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY